

14th NORTH AMERICAN MASONRY CONFERENCE

Omaha, NE, USA | June 11-14, 2023

Development of a Sag Resistance Test for Plasters and Renders

Monika Pultorak^{a*}, Paulo B. Lourenço^a, Miguel Azenha^a

^a University of Minho, ISISE, ARISE, Department of Civil Engineering, Guimaraes, Portugal

Abstract:

Sagging is a phenomenon that occurs in paints, coats, renders and plasters applied on vertical surfaces. It is a vertical downward flow of the material caused by gravitational forces observed immediately after application, that results in an uneven surface. Sagging can be caused by applying excessively thick layers, over-thinning of the material, insufficient adhesion, or application under high humidity environment. For plasters or renders, sag resistance is important because sagging may cause aesthetic, functional and durability problems. Nonetheless, there is no commonly accepted test for evaluating this phenomenon in mortar, with professionals normally relying on trials on actual walls. The standard ASTM D4400, devised for measurement of sagging in paints, was used as an inspiration for the proposal of a sag resistance test for renders and plasters within the present paper. In ASTM D4400, the multi-notch applicator creates parallel lines of the paint under testing on a special chart with different layer thickness evenly distributed with a known distance between them. The chart is then hung vertically (with the paint lines following the horizontal direction) to begin the sagging test. By evaluating the gaps between lines after sagging, it is possible to determine a quantitative result based on the assessment of the first line from the bottom that does not touch the layer below.

This work proposes a sag resistance test for renders and plasters at laboratory-scale test using one brick and a 3D printed multinotch applicator. The applicator was designed to create two lines of mortar with 2 cm of thickness which is considered representative of thick one-coat layer. Then the material is left undisturbed on the substrate to initiate sagging. The goal of this sag resistance test for plasters and renders is to create a simple, representative and cost-effective test to replace the traditional trial-and-error approach.

Keywords: Sag Resistance, Plasters, Renders, Fresh Mortars, Quality Check, Material Testing

*Corresponding author email address: monika.pultorak@civil.uminho.pt

1 Introduction

Renders and plasters are mortars applied on vertical surface of exterior and interior walls, respectively (CEN, 2011). Both materials are used for protective and decorative purposes of the substrate wall, which is in turn normally made from stone, brick or even adobe. Renders and plasters have been used since prehistoric times (Groot et al., 2012). In ancient times mainly lime renders and plaster were used but with the development of Portland cement, they were mostly replaced in favour of the latter (Nogueira et al., 2018). Unlike the case of mortars for structural purposes, strength is not the main basic requirement for rendering and plastering mortars. The most important requirements for renders and plasters are good adhesion and aesthetic, smooth, even surface (Sandin, 1995). These factors depend significantly on the fresh properties. In terms of application procedure, it is frequent nowadays to use processes of machine plastering/rendering. During the machine spraying of the mortar the material endures high shear stresses first during pumping the material to the nozzle and then in the nozzle itself when it has to be sprayed onto the substrate. Once the material is on the wall it must quickly recover the yield stress to overcome the forces of gravity to avoid sagging (Kaci et al., 2011; Kolakowska & Kristiansen, 2009).

Sagging is a defect as the result of excessive flow on vertical surfaces which creates an uneven and unaesthetic surface with accumulation of the material (Croll & Kisha, 1992; Wang et al., 2021). This phenomenon is well-known in paints and coats. These materials are tested for sag resistance by a standardized method from ASTM D4400 (ASTM, 2018). A specially designed device called multinotch applicator or Anti-Sag meter is used to create the stripes of paint or coat which are evaluated further for sagging. Naturally, plasters and renders tend to flow down like paint or coating when applied on vertical surfaces of substrates (Banfill, 2006). Literature about the evaluation of sagging in mortars, renders and plasters is scarce. Sagging is still evaluated on trials on actual walls (Arikan & Sobolev, 2002) or by using the rheological measurements (Fernandez-Ibarburu A et al., 2016).

This paper proposes a Sag Resistance Test focused on fresh properties of rendering and plastering mortars. The sagging is analyzed qualitatively by experimental studies of the behavior of fresh ready-mix mortar on clay thermic brick after the movement of designed device inspired by multinotch applicator from ASTM D4400 (ASTM, 2018). The proposed test setup and device were created to assess the possibility of upscaling the test from the paints and coats level to apply it to renders and plasters (mortar level). This paper presents some initial developments that solely comprise qualitative assessments, whereas the method has the potential to become quantitative through explicit measurement of the downward movement of the fresh render/plaster. The proposed test method has the potential to be lab-scale, simple, representative, quick and cost-effective, hence possibly replacing the traditional trial-and-error tests that are normally applied in-situ.

2 Background of the sag resistance test for paints

The test proposed in this paper is inspired by the ASTM D4400 Sag Resistance test for Paints Using a Multinotch Applicator (ASTM, 2018). This test is used to evaluate the sagging and levelling of the paint and coats. The present Section of the paper provides some details about D4400 method, in order to assist the understanding of the proposal for mortars to be made in Section 3.

2.1 Apparatus

The multinotch Applicator or Leneta Anti-Sag Meter (see Figure 1) is a device with a series of notches of successively higher clearance from the thickest on the bottom to the thinnest on the top of the device (Lade et al., 2015). This device creates 11 parallel layers of paint with different thicknesses separated by constant

gaps between them (Figures 1 and 2) on a special testing chart to assess the degree of sagging given by a numerical value called Anti-Sag Index. Not only the gaps between the layers are constant but also the height of the layers that are created using this device.

Figure 1. Scheme of multinotch applicator (Anti-Sag Meter) with the dimension of the gap between the notches (notch separation) and the notch width (the height of layers created)

Table 1. The notch depths (clearances) for Anti-Sag Meters (ASTM, 2018)

Range	For coating type	Notch Clearances											
		Mils	4	6	8	10	12	14	16	18	20	22	24
Medium	Water borne architectural	μm	100	150	200	250	300	350	400	450	500	550	600
		Mils	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	
Standard	Solvent-borne architectural	μm	75	100	125	150	175	200	225	250	275	300	
		Mils	1	1.5	2	2.5	3	3.5	4	4.5	5	5.5	6
Low	Industrial O.E.M. coatings	μm	25	38	50	63	75	88	100	113	125	138	150
		Mils	14	16	18	20	25	30	35	40	45	50	60
High	High build coatings	μm	350	400	450	500	625	750	875	1000	1125	1250	1500
		Mils											

The testing chart is a special test surface which is a sealed and smooth paper test. The chart may be plain white or white and black, depending on the tone of the paint to be tested (ASTM, 2018).

2.2 The procedure of the test

The entire procedure with steps is shown in Figure 2. The first step is to thoroughly stir the paint or coat. The syringe needle is immersed in the material and collects 8ml of paint (Figure 2a). The straightedge guide which helps in moving the applicator has to be fastened to the drawdown plate. The applicator has to be placed at the end of the chart with fixation to the straightedge guide which helps in steady movement of the applicator. All the items of the setup have to be placed horizontally (Figure 2b). When the setup is ready, the paint is applied from the syringe to the chart between the arms of the applicator (Figure 2c). Then the material is pulled at a constant speed of 150 mm/s by the applicator (Figure 2d). After conducting the movement the chart is immediately hung up with the thickest stripe at the bottom on the chart (ASTM, 2018), as shown in Figure 2e. In this moment the gravitational forces start to act on the layers to cause the sagging and the cohesive forces have to counteract them to prevent the material to sag (Kolakowska & Kristiansen, 2009). The test chart is left until the paint is dry and ready for evaluation (Figure 2f). The clearance at which no sagging is observed is taken as the thickness up to which a coating can be applied without sagging and is called Sag Index (Bhavsar & Shreepathi, 2016).

Figure 2. Scheme of the steps of the Sag Resistance Test for Paints, with figures b,c,d corresponding to the stage over a flat surface and figures e,f, corresponding to the testing chart on a vertical position

3 Proposed Sag Resistance Test for Plasters and Renders

The proposed test is inspired by ASTM D4400 for paints and coats. The idea was to create the device for creating layers of mortar on the testing substrate and then evaluate the sagging phenomenon. Naturally, the size of the device has to be bigger. The device was upscaled and a brick was considered to replace the testing chart as the substrate for the renders and plasters. Clay perforated thermic bricks with the dimensions of 30cm x 30 cm x 19 cm were used for the purpose of this test. The bricks were stored in the basement of the laboratory under constant environment conditions. There was no special preparation of the surface of the bricks such as the use of a primer or prewetting the surface for better bonding of the brick surface with fresh mortar or to prevent the water transport from fresh mortar into the brick. The condition of the bricks can be considered as dry. This condition is similar of real-case application condition.

3.1 Testing device – multinotch applicator

The proposed applicator was designed in CAD software and 3D printed using PLA (polylactide) filament. The surface of the device was smoothed with sandpaper. The dimensions of the device can be seen in Figure 3. The device geometry ensures to create the two layers of render/plaster with a height of 6 cm and 2cm of thickness for each layer. The thickness of 2 cm was chosen as representative of a very thick one-coat mortar. The gap between layers is set for 2 cm. The layers themselves are placed symmetrically to the center of the brick so the distance from the horizontal edges of the brick to the layers of the mortar is 2,5 cm because the brick height is 19 cm.

Figure 3. The proposed geometry of multinotch applicator for sag resistance test for renders and plaster

3.2 Proposed procedure of the test

In first developments towards establishing the sag resistance test for renders and plasters the procedure was implemented from ASTM D4400 with some differences. The face of the brick as substrate replacing the testing chart is placed horizontally as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Scheme of the steps from 1 to 4 of the proposed Sag Resistance Test for Plasters and Renders.

The brick and whole setup has to be ready before preparing the mortar to test. The prepared and mixed fresh mortar is applied by a trowel on the brick surface on the whole length of the brick face in two parts where the layers will be made by the applicator (Figure 4-1). At this point, the applicator is applied and fitted as close as possible to the left edge of the brick (Figure 4-2). Subsequently, while holding the device on the outer perpendicular walls of the device and pressing the device from two planes towards the brick, the movement along the length of the brick must be performed as quickly as possible to form the layers (Figure 4-3). Two ready layers to be tested are shown on the right picture in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Two layers created for the Sag Resistance Test right after the movement of the multinotch applicator with the face of the brick in the horizontal position right before the rotation

As the layers are finished, the brick with layers is rotated 90° to a vertical position (Figure 4-4) and placed on the edge of the table or on an elevation, such as a stand, with the free flowing of the layers allowed. In this position the gravitational forces start to act on the layers. The end of the rotation of the brick is correlated as ‘time zero’ (0 min). The clock starts right after the movement and the layers are observed for 20 minutes. After reaching 20 minutes the test is considered to be finished. The whole test is recorded by a camera.

3.3 Materials

3.3.1 Ready-mix mortar for plastering/rendering

A ready-mix dry mortar for plastering and rendering from Axton was used. The ready-mix render/plaster is composed mainly of Portland cement and aggregate with the incorporation of chemical admixtures. The maximum thickness of this render/plaster possible to achieve is declared on the package as 2 cm. In this test, the only factor that was manipulated was the water content. For one bag including 25 kg of ready-mix mortar the range of water that can be added is between 3,5 and 6,1 liters. For every test, the amount of dry ready-mix mortar was determined to 3 kg. Based on the range provided by the manufacturer, 4 distinct water contents for mixes were considered (in the brackets there are names that will be further used in this paper):

- Maximum amount of water required for 3kg of dry ready-mix mortar (MAX water)
- +10% amount of water by weight from the maximum required amount of water (+10% water)
- +15% amount of water by weight from the maximum required amount of water (+15% water)
- +20% amount of water by weight from the maximum required amount of water (+20% water)

The intent was to have different degrees of underperforming mortars in terms of sagging, so the choice was to go over the maximum limit of water recommended by the manufacturer. The aforementioned mixes were carefully mixed manually until visibly well mixed and uniform consistency without any agglomerated particles. The flow table test was performed for each mix immediately after the mixing procedure. As a characterization of the mortar, only the consistency of the mortar by flow table test was carried out in accordance with EN 1015-3 (CEN, 1999). The composition of the mixes and the results of flow table test are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Mix composition and flow table values of the mixes

Mix	Ready-mix dry mortar content	Water content	Flow table value
MAX water	3 kg	0,73 kg	194 mm
+10% water	3 kg	0,80 kg	208,5 mm
+15% water	3 kg	0,84 kg	214,5 mm
+20% water	3 kg	0,88 kg	224,5 mm

4 Results and discussion

The results of the sagging tests are shown in Figures 6, 7, 8 and 9. The results are presented for each mix in two pictures, except for the case of Figure 9. On the left the photos were taken immediately after the rotation of the brick to the testing vertical position, that is, at the so-called zero time (0 min), whereas the photos on the right were taken when the test was finished, therefore after remaining the rotated brick with layers to be tested for 20 min. The results are presented for the four mixes mentioned previously. As can be seen in Figure 6 for the mix with the maximum possible amount of water as prescribed by the supplier, there is no visible change in shape of the layers during the 20 min of test, hence concluding that sagging was not observed. It was however found that the quality of layers is poor, as they seem to have uneven height and lack of smoothness, pointing to the need for improvements in further attempts of this experimental technique. In Figure 7 the quality of the completed layers is better but still not considered acceptable. Slight sagging can be observed but at a seemingly acceptable level which does not seem affect the performance of this render in a relevant manner. In Figure 8, the sagging phenomenon can be seen very clearly on the lower layer on the left, and slight sagging on the upper layer on the right. After 20 minutes of observation and drying the grains of the fine particles of the aggregate, it can be seen and that the left side of the lower layer has sagged slightly more at the end of the experiment. In Figure 9 there is only one photo caused by excessive sagging just after the brick was turned, which caused the material to completely slip off the substrate. The layers are indistinguishable as they joined together and the mortar flowed down the brick. In all cases, the quality of the layers near the vertical edges of the brick is questionable.

Figure 6. Results of mix with maximum possible content after 0 min (on the left) and 20 min (on the right)

Figure 7. Results of mix with 10% more water than maximum possible content after 0 min (on the left) and 20 min (on the right)

Figure 8. Results of a mix with 15 % more water than maximum possible content after 0 min (on the left) and 20 min (on the right)

Figure 9. Results of a mix with 20 % more water than maximum possible content right after the movement of the device (0 min)

As can be observed from Figure 6 to Figure 8 the more liquid the mortar is, the better the quality of the layers meaning the evenness and filling of the shape in height and width through all length of the substrate. As in all Figures the quality of the layers on the vertical edges of the brick is questionable it can be treated as boundary conditions that should be not considered in the overall evaluation of sagging.

5 Conclusions

The initial steps of towards a new Sag Resistance Test for mortars shown in this paper are considered promising in continuing to develop the method and could be a useful tool for quality check in the industry. The test is easy to handle and could save time, material and money while replacing the trials of renders and plasters on actual wall. The trials showed that the phenomenon of sagging appears in renders and plasters and when the mortar is too liquid then the mortar is more prone to sagging. As trials showed the potential of the test there are still some developments considered to avoid observed obstacles such as:

- Plastering/rendering the brick in a vertical position of the brick face, rather than horizontally, as was done in this initial trial, to avoid excessive force acting on the plaster/render when rotating the brick 90°, resulting in excessive sagging, as seen in Figure 9.
- Plastering/rendering the entire brick without dividing it into parts where the layers are to be made to reproduce the actual plastering/rendering process on the construction site.
- A probable change in the geometry of the device to maintain the scale ratio from the original Leneta Anti-Sag Meter and to evaluate different but most common thicknesses for one-coat plastering/rendering mortars in a single test.
- The poor quality of the layers should be improved by changing the geometry of the device or setup due to inconsistency in shape and parallelism of the layers to each other.
- Quantitative measurements are desirable to obtain a value in mm of how much the layer has sagged to improve the test

As trials showed the potential of the test to be a useful tool for quality check in industry. The multinotch applicator will be further developed with the upgrades to overcome the listed obstacles in conclusions. To sum up, the test is feasible but needs further studies which are planned to improve the test and its setup.

6 Acknowledgments

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Marie Skłodowska-Curie project SUBLime - Sustainable Building Lime applications via Circular Economy and Biomimetic Approaches [Grant Agreement n.955986].

This work was partly financed by FCT/MCTES through national funds (PIDDAC) under the R&D Unit Institute for Sustainability and Innovation in Structural Engineering (ISISE), under reference UIDB/04029/2020.

7 References

- Arikan, M., & Sobolev, K. (2002). "The optimization of a gypsum-based composite material." *Cement and Concrete Research*, 32(11), 1725–1728.
- ASTM. (2018). *ASTM D4400 Standard Test Method for Sag Resistance of Paints Using a Multinotch Applicator*.
- Banfill, P. F. G. (2006). "Rheology of Fresh Cement and Concrete." *Rheology of Fresh Cement and Concrete*, 61–130.
- Bhavsar, R., & Shreepathi, S. (2016). "Evolving empirical rheological limits to predict flow-levelling and sag resistance of waterborne architectural paints." *Progress in Organic Coatings*, 101, 15–23.
- CEN. (1999). *BS EN 1015-3:1999 Methods of test for mortar for masonry - Part 3 : Determination of consistence of fresh mortar (by flow table)*.

- CEN. (2011). *EN 998-1:2010 Specification for mortar for masonry - Part 1: Rendering and plastering mortar*.
- Croll, S. G., & Kisha, L. W. (1992). "Observations of sagging in architectural paints." *Progress in Organic Coatings*, 20(1), 27–52.
- Fernandez-Ibarburu A, Diaz del Castillo P., & Gonzalez D. (2016). "A new empirical test method for evaluation sag/slip control and workability in mortars containing mineral rheological additives." In *Rheologische Messungen an Baustoffen 2016: Tagungsband zum 25. .*
- Groot, C., Hughes, J. J., van Balen, K., Bicer-Simsir, B., Binda, L., Elsen, J., van Hees, R., von Konow, T., Lindqvist, J. E., Maurenbrecher, P., Papayanni, I., Subercaseaux, M., Tedeschi, C., Toumbakari, E. E., Thompson, M., Valek, J., Veiga, R., Blauer, C., Middendorf, B., ... Vanhellefont, Y. (2012). "RILEM TC 203-RHM: Repair mortars for historic masonry: Performance requirements for renders and plasters." *Materials and Structures/Materiaux et Constructions*, 45(9), 1277–1285.
- Kaci, A., Chaouche, M., & Andréani, P. A. (2011). "Influence of bentonite clay on the rheological behaviour of fresh mortars." *Cement and Concrete Research*, 41(4), 373–379.
- Kolakowska, E., & Kristiansen, M. (2009). "Automation of paint sag measurement and prediction for paint planning and scheduling." *Proceedings of the IASTED International Conference on Identification, Control, and Applications, ICA 2009, March*, 15–21.
- Lade, R. K., Musliner, A. D., Macosko, C. W., & Francis, L. F. (2015). "Evaluating sag resistance with a multinotched applicator: correlation with surface flow measurements and practical recommendations." *Journal of Coatings Technology and Research*, 12(5), 809–817.
- Nogueira, R., Ferreira Pinto, A. P., & Gomes, A. (2018). "Design and behavior of traditional lime-based plasters and renders. Review and critical appraisal of strengths and weaknesses." *Cement and Concrete Composites*, 89, 192–204.
- Sandin, K. (1995). "Mortars for Masonry and Rendering Choice and Application." *Building Issues*, 7(3).
- Wang, C. S., Chapelle, G., Carreau, P., & Heuzey, M. C. (2021). "Prediction of sag resistance in paints using rheological measurements." *Progress in Organic Coatings*, 153(May 2020).